

Finite Element Simulation of Strain Measurement in Auxetic Materials via FBG Sensors

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Abstract—Auxetic materials are increasingly used in biomedical and aerospace applications. Fibre Bragg grating sensors are well-known in non-destructive testing for their precision. This work simulates a tensile test of two auxetic specimens with embedded sensors and compares the results with experimental data to validate the model.

Keywords— metamaterials, auxetic, NDT/SHM, FBG sensor.

I. INTRODUCTION

Auxetic materials are a class of metamaterials that, as a defining feature, have a negative Poisson ratio [1]. It means that these materials, under tension, expand in the directions orthogonal to the applied load. Conversely, under compression, they collapse in directions perpendicular to the applied load. A schematic of auxetic behaviour compared with normal material under tension is shown in Fig.1 As a consequence

Fig. 1. On top normal material behaviour. Below auxetic material behaviour.

of this peculiar behaviour, these materials exhibit interesting features, such as increased shear, indentation and fracture resistance; synclastic behaviour, which means that if these structures are subjected to an out-of-plane bending moment, they show a dome shape; moreover, due to their deformation method, it is possible to exploit them as a variable permeability [2]. Fibre Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors are composed of an optical fibre in which a grating is inscribed. To obtain the grating, the refractive index of the fibre is modified to form a periodic pattern. As a result, this structure can reflect light

with a specific wavelength. It is possible to calculate the exact reflected wavelength using the following formula [3]:

$$\lambda_B = 2n\Lambda, \quad (1)$$

in this formula, λ_B represents the Bragg wavelength, which is the reflected wavelength, n is the effective refractive index, and Λ is the periodicity of the sensor. As it is possible to infer from the formula, this kind of sensors are sensitive to deformation. In fact, when the fibre is stretched, the reflected wave shows a redshift (the reflection happens for a higher wavelength). On the contrary, during compression, the reflected wave shows a blueshift (the reflection happens for a lower wavelength). This is caused by the action of the deformation on the periodicity of the grating and on the effective refractive index. Furthermore, these sensors are sensitive to temperature, which is because temperature can also affect the periodicity of the grating through the thermal expansion coefficient and the effective refractive index through the thermal-optic effect. The relationship between the Bragg wavelength, strain and temperature is made explicit in the following formula [4]:

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda}{\lambda_B} = (1 - p)(\epsilon + \alpha\Delta T) + \xi\Delta T, \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta\lambda$ represents the shift of the reflected wavelength, λ_B the Bragg wavelength, p the coefficient of the photo-elastic effect, ϵ the deformation, α the thermal-expansion coefficient, ΔT the temperature difference, and ξ the thermal-optic coefficient. The possibility of monitoring auxetic materials using FBG sensors could have some potential due to the increasing importance of auxetic materials and the interesting features of FBG sensors. Nevertheless, this possibility is still poorly explored in the literature. In this paper, we want to investigate the possibility of simulating the behaviour of an FBG sensor attached to the surface of an auxetic material for measuring the stretching of the structure.

II. METHODS

In previous work [5], it was demonstrated that it is feasible to attach a Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) sensor to the surface of an auxetic structure without significantly altering its mechanical behaviour. Building upon this foundation, the present study aims to develop a comprehensive numerical model of an FBG sensor using COMSOL Multiphysics, with the objective of

simulating the sensor's response under tensile strain. The modeling process will proceed in several steps. First, the FBG sensor will be represented as a discrete element with appropriate material properties and geometrical parameters. a picture on the grating modelled in COMSOL is shown in Fig. 2. Subsequently, the auxetic specimen will be simulated under

Fig. 2. Schematic of the grating geometry implemented in COMSOL.

controlled tensile loading conditions, providing a detailed map of the strain distribution at the location where the sensor is attached. Using the obtained deformation field, we will then apply the corresponding strain to the FBG model in order to predict the resulting Bragg wavelength shift, based on the well-known relationships that link strain to changes in the optical response of the sensor. This approach enables a direct correlation between the mechanical deformation of the structure and the optical signal generated by the FBG. Figure 3 shows the redshift predicted by the model for a simple tensile simulation, and the blueshift resulting from a compression simulation. Finally, the simulated wavelength shifts

Fig. 3. FBG reflectance peak shifts under mechanical load: compression (blue) causes a blueshift, tension (red) induces a redshift, and the unloaded state (green).

will be processed to calculate the corresponding measured strains. These numerical predictions will be compared with experimental data obtained from physical testing of the sensor-embedded auxetic specimens. Through this comparison, we

aim to validate the accuracy of the FBG model. The outcomes of this study will not only provide a validated computational framework for simulating FBG sensors in complex structures but also enhance the understanding of the interplay between auxetic deformation and optical sensing, paving the way for more advanced structural health monitoring applications.

III. CONCLUSION

This work proposes a numerical approach for simulating the behaviour of a Fibre Bragg Grating sensor attached to an auxetic structure under tensile loading. The developed model, implemented in COMSOL Multiphysics, aims to establish a correlation between the strain field generated in the auxetic material and the corresponding Bragg wavelength shift of the sensor. At this stage, the study focuses on defining the modelling strategy and the procedure that will be used to predict the optical response of the FBG based on the mechanical deformation of the structure. The comparison with future experimental results will allow validation of the proposed framework and assessment of its reliability. The presented methodology represents a preliminary step toward the integration of FBG sensors in auxetic materials for structural health monitoring applications.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. S. Shuaibu, J. Deng, C. Xu, V. P. Ade-Oke, A. Aliyu, and D. Momoh, "Advancing auxetic materials: Emerging development and innovative applications," *Reviews on Advanced Materials Science*, vol. 63, no. 1, 2024, Art. no. 0021, doi: 10.1515/rams-2024-0021.
- [2] X. Ren, R. Das, P. Tran, T. D. Ngo, and Y. M. Xie, "Auxetic metamaterials and structures: A review," *Smart Materials and Structures*, vol. 27, no. 2, 2018, Art. no. 023001, doi: 10.1088/1361-665X/aaa61c.
- [3] J. K. Sahota, N. Gupta, and D. Dhawan, "Fiber Bragg grating sensors for monitoring of physical parameters: A comprehensive review," *Optical Engineering*, vol. 59, no. 6, 2020, Art. no. 060901, doi: 10.1117/1.oe.59.6.060901.
- [4] X. Li, J. Long, S. Guo, M. Yang, T. Zhang, C. An, and Y. Pei, "Experimental study on FBG sensing technology-based stress monitoring at the corners of reinforced soil retaining walls," *Science Progress*, vol. 105, no. 4, 2022, doi: 10.1177/00368504221135380.
- [5] R. Moroni, A. Andrearczyk, and K. Majewska, "Monitoring auxetic structure with FBG sensor," *e-Journal of Nondestructive Testing*, vol. 31, no. 2, 2026, doi: 10.58286/32439.